

22NRM01 TraMeXI

D4 Recommendations on the specific requirements enabling traceable clinical measurements with the targeted uncertainty 7 % (k = 2) Version v2 (corrected)

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Glossary

CEM contrast-enhanced mammography

conv conventional

DBT digital breast tomosynthesis

HVL half-value layer

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1 Introduction

This document describes recommendations on specific requirements such as compliance tests and rated ranges for reference- and field-class dosimeters to enable traceable clinical measurements with the targeted uncertainty 7 % ($k = 2$)^a and to be updated in future revisions of IEC 61674 and evidence submitted to IEC SC62C WG 3 and IAEA CRP E24024 officers.

^aThe uncertainty contributions covered by the target uncertainty are described in chapter 9.

1.1 Corrections Version v2

This corrected version addresses an error in the calculation of the uncertainty budget presented in Section 9. Additionally, the tables in Section 3 have been updated in accordance with the latest version of D1.

2 Current state influence quantities and rated ranges IEC 61674

Influence quantities and performance characteristics	Minimum rated range	Limits of variation	Chapter IEC 61674:2012
Dose linearity ^a		2 %	5.1
Repeatability ^a		Depends on quantity and dose rate	5.2
Resolution of reading		1 %	5.3
Stabilisation time ^a		2 %	5.4
Pulsed radiation ^a	1 ms	2 %	5.5
Resets		1 %	5.6 (removed in 61674:2024)
Leakage current		1 %	5.7 (removed in 61674:2024)
Long term stability		2 % per year	5.8.1
Accumulated air kerma (lifetime dose) ^a	40 Gy	1 %	5.8.2
Radiation quality	Depends on modality	5 %	6.2
Air kerma rate	Stated by the manufacturer	2 %	6.3
Angle of radiation incidence	Non-CT: 5 ° CT: 180 °	3 %	6.4
Operation voltage	Mains: -15 % - 10 %, Batteries: stated by the manufacturer	2 %	6.5
Air pressure	80 kPa – 106 kPa	2 %	6.6
Air pressure equilibrium time	10 %	2 %	6.7

Temperature and rel. humidity	15 °C to 35 °C, < 80 %	3 %	6.8
Electromagnetic compatibility	IEC 61000-4	5 %	6.9
Field size	not less than 35 cm x 35 cm	3 %	6.10

^anot listed as a minimum rated range but mandatory requirement in a compliance test

2.1 Energy dependence of the response IEC 61674:2024

In IEC 61674, the minimum rated ranges for radiation qualities are split into different modalities. The limit of variation is 5 % within each modality.

Modality	Minimum rated range	Range Al-filtration [mm] ^a	Range Cu-filtration [mm]	Range HVL [mm Al]
Mammography	Stated by the manufacturer	-	-	-
Conventional (unattenuated)	RQR 3 - 10	2 - 5	-	1.78 - 6.57
Conventional (attenuated)	RQA 3 - 10	12 - 50	-	3.8 - 13.3
CT	RQR 8 - 10 RQT 8 - 10 RQA 5 - 9	2.5 - 5 2.5 - 5 23.5 - 44.2	- 0.2 - 0.3 -	3.97 - 11.5
Copper-filtered beams	RQC 3 - 8	2.25 - 3.75	0.5 - 2.0	4.5 - 11.5

^aAl filtration for IEC radiation qualities depends on the inherent filtration and anode angle, for some X-ray tubes the maximum Al filtration can be up to 2 mm Al smaller (if highest energy is RQR 10 based) and the minimum additional filtration can be up to 2.5 mm Al larger (if lowest energy is RQR 8 based).

3 Clinically relevant and physical representative radiation qualities (CPRQs)

3.1 Copper and aluminium filtrations

For CT, it is known that one manufacturer also uses Ag filtration, but no technical details were shared with the consortium.

Modality	Range voltage [kV]	Range Al-filtration [mm]	Range Cu-filtration [mm]	Range HVL [mm Al]
Diagnostic radiography	50 - 130	2.5 - 4.5	0 - 0.3	1.7 - 9.4
C-arms, mobile	50 - 120	2.7 - 5.8	0 - 0.2	1.4 - 9.3

C-arms, stationary	60 - 150	2.5 - 3.5	0 - 0.9	2.1- 12.6
Dental, intraoral	50 - 70	1.5	-	1.3 - 1.8
Dental, extraoral, including CBCT	60 - 120	2.5 - 4.5	0 - 0.5	2.2 - 10.2
CT	70 - 150	2.5 - 10	-	2.4 - 9.4

3.2 Tin filtration

Modality	Range voltage [kV]	Range Al-filtration [mm]	Range Sn-filtration [mm]	Range HVL [mm Al]
CT	100 - 150	6 - 7	0.4 - 0.85	10.3 - 15.2

3.3 Gold filtration

Modality	Range voltage [kV]	Range Al-filtration [mm]	Range Au-filtration [mm]	Range HVL [mm Al]
CT	120 - 140	6 - 7.5	0.07	9.3 - 10.3

3.4 Mammography

Anode Materials	Filter Material	Range thickness [μm]	Voltage range (A 1.1.3) [keV]	Range HVL [mm Al] ^{a, b}	Comments
Mo	Mo	30	20 - 35	0.1 - 0.6	conv, DBT
Mo Rh (GE)	Rh	25, 30 (Instrumentarium)	20 - 35 -	0.2 - 0.7 -	conv, DBT
Mo, Rh	Cu	250	49	-	CEM (GE ^e)
Rh	Ag	30	20 - 35	0.3 - 0.7	conv (GE ^e), DBT
W	Rh	50, 60 (Planmed)	20 - 40 -	0.3 - 0.9	conv, DBT
W	Ag	50, 75 (Planmed)	20 - 40	0.3 - 1.0	conv, DBT
W	Al	500 - 1000	20 - 50	0.2 - 1.3	conv, DBT, CEM
W	Ti	1000 - 1300	49	3.1 - 3.7	CEM (Siemens)
W	Cu	300	45, 50	2.9 - 3.8	CEM (Hologic)

^aLower limits have been rounded down and upper limits have been rounded up.

^bThe upper limit of the HVL range has been calculated taking into account a compression paddle, which has been conservatively estimated by increasing the upper HVL value by 0.2 mm Al, the effect of tube aging was not considered for the given ranges and can lead to an additional increase of 12 % in HVL values.

^dconventional (conv), contrast-enhanced mammography (CEM), digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT)

^eGeneral Electric (manufacturer)

The voltage range is 20 to 50 kV, where voltages above 35 kV were only reported for contrast-enhanced mammography.

The results showed that tungsten is the most common anode material for the reported devices (13) followed by molybdenum (5). Only two devices with rhodium anodes were reported (Senographe Pristina and Essential, GE, USA). It must be noted that a specific filter thickness is linked with a specific anode material. E.g., the typical thickness of Rh filters for Molybdenum anodes is 25 μm , while 50 μm is the most used thickness for W anodes (5 scanners were identified). This filter is also used for tomosynthesis by some manufacturers (Siemens, Planmed).

Another common filter is 50 μm of Ag, this was found for 4 scanner models (Giotto, Hologic, United Imaging). One manufacturer (Planmed) has a deviating thickness for Ag filters (75 μm).

Some manufacturers also use Al filters for tomosynthesis, e.g., 700 μm Al filters for (Hologic, Fuji), there's also one device using 500 μm Al (Metaltronica).

For contrast enhanced mammography also Cu and Ti filters are relevant. These filters are used for the high energy radiation field between 45 and 49 keV.

4 Reference-class dosimeters

It is recommended to introduce requirements for reference-class dosimeters. Reference-class dosimeters are understood as defined in IEC 60731:2001: dosimeter whose performance and stability are sufficient for it to be used to calibrate other dosimeters. Reference-class dosimeters could be introduced with more strict requirements as a separate class in IEC 61674 or in a separate standard.

For the purposes of this document, all other dosimeters are defined as field-class dosimeters.

5 Recommended new rated ranges

5.1 Radiation qualities

5.1.1 Conventional

It is recommended that the new RQC radiation conditions be included in the minimum rated ranges for dosimeters tested for conventional modality. The new RQC radiation conditions are described in TraMeXI deliverable 1. These radiation conditions mimic the thin copper filters found in conventional equipment.

5.1.2 Dental

It is recommended that a new minimum rated range is defined for dental applications. This should include the new RQC radiation qualities and the new dental radiation qualities (for intraoral applications). These will be described in TraMeXI deliverable 1.

5.1.3 Mammography

The most common anode filter combination in mammography is a tungsten anode with 50 μm Rh filtration. Therefore, a dosimeter sold for measurements in mammography should be capable of performing measurements for this combination. It is recommended to include this in the rated ranges within IEC 61676.

As this does not cover all devices and future developments may introduce new combinations, consideration should be given to removing tabulated values for mammography from the standard.

5.1.4 CT

The new RQC radiation conditions are recommended to be added to the minimum rated range for CT.

5.1.5 Reference-class dosimeters

For reference class dosimeters, it is recommended to define a full range criterion combining the HVL range of the conventional modalities (unattenuated and attenuated) as well C-arm, dental and CT with its own limit of variation. This is recommended to be tested using RQR, the new RQC and RQA radiation conditions. In addition, more stringent requirements are recommended for certain ranges of radiation conditions, depending on the modality in which the dosimeters are to be used.

The following table shows the HVL range recommended for the full range criterion.

Modality	Old range HVL [mm Al]	New range HVL [mm Al]
Conventional (unattenuated)	1.78 - 6.57	1.4 – 13.3 (RQR, new RQC, RQA, CCRI)
C-arm	-	
Dental	-	
Conventional (attenuated)	3.8 – 13.3	

Reference-class dosimeters used for mammography do not need to meet the full range criterion, but it is recommended that all radiation conditions described in 5.1.3 be included in the minimum rated range. The recommended reference conditions are a tungsten anode with additional filtration of 0,7 cm Al.

Reference-class dosimeters should also be tested for CCRI radiation conditions used for BIPM key comparisons.

6 Recommended new limits of variation

6.1 Reference class dosimeters

Several detectors were identified within the project that are considered reference-class dosimeters. It was shown that these can hold stricter limits of variation: 1 % for linearity, 0.5 % for stabilization time, 0.5 % for long term stability, 1 % for angle of radiation incidence and air kerma rate, and 1 % for angle of radiation incidence.

6.1.1 Energy dependence response

Full range criterion

The recommended limit of variation for the full range criterion is 4.5 %. The project has shown that dosimeters exist that can meet this requirement.

Conventional

In addition, it is recommended that reference class dosimeters be within a limit of variation of 1.5 % if tested within the series RQR, the new RQC and RQA.

Mammography

For dosimeters which are designed explicitly for mammography, the full range criterion is not recommended. For these a limit of variation of 1 % is recommended, for a minimum rated range, that includes all anode filter combinations described in section 3.4.

6.2 Field-class dosimeters

6.2.1 Resolution of reading

A comparison of the performance of the dosimeters tested in the project shows that stricter limits are recommended for the influence of the following quantities: resolution of the reading, stabilization time and angle of incident radiation.

6.3 Influence quantities with high uncertainty contributions

Reviewing the current limit of variations, it was found that electromagnetic compatibility has one of the largest contributions to the uncertainty budget. Further research should be conducted to investigate if this limit can be lowered. Some manufacturers have noted within the scope of the project that this limit could be lowered.

High uncertainty contributions were also identified for the operating voltage, air pressure, and temperature.

7 Recommended new compliance tests

7.1 Rotation

A new compliance test for the dependence of the response of dosimeters on rotation of the detector is recommended. The recommended limit of variation is 0.5 %. The minimum rated range is recommended to be stated by the manufacturer.

8 Recommended new definitions

8.1 Field size

In the current version, IEC 61674 gives a minimum rated range of maximum field size of not less than 35 cm x 35 cm. On the other hand, there is no clear definition of the quantity field size within the standard. It is clear that the spectral distribution and intensity of the radiation beam within the field size should be constant for radiation conditions used for testing equipment. This aspect is also not described in IEC 61267.

Some ideas to define a field size can be found in literature. TRS-457 states, that the variation of air kerma rate over the central 80 % of the cross-sectional area of the beam used for calibration should be less than 2 %. A suitable definition could also be based on identifying the field size as the umbra region, which can be directly calculated from the focus size and the collimation.

8.2 Pulse length

There is no clear definition of pulse length in IEC 61267. On the other hand, some compliance tests are performed for specific pulse lengths. A harmonized definition of pulse length, which is also used for testing, is needed. (e.g., based ISO 18090-1).

8.3 Kerma rate

There are several requirements regarding air kerma rate, but a clear definition for the scenario of pulsed radiation is missing in IEC 61267.

9 Uncertainty reference-class dosimeters

The following table shows the uncertainty budget for a reference class-dosimeter under consideration of the recommended limits of variation.

Influence Quantity	Uncertainty [%] (k = 1)
Calibration coefficient	1.0 (typical SSDL calibration)
Radiation quality	0.87 (conventional)
Air kerma rate	0.58

Angle of radiation incidence	0.58
Rotation	0.29
Dose linearity	0.58
Air pressure	1.15
Temperature	1.73
Electromagnetic combability	2.89
Field size	1.73
Operating voltage	1.15
Long term stability	0.29
Stabilization time	0.29
Resolution of reading	0.29
Relative combined standard uncertainty (k = 1)	4.48
Relative expanded standard uncertainty (k = 2)	8.96

If the limit of variation of the electromagnetic combability could be reduced to 1 % and limit of variation for the operating voltage could be reduced to 0.5 %, a relative expanded standard uncertainty below 6.6 % could be achieved.

The same calculation applied to the limits of variation for non-reference-class equipment gives a relative expanded standard uncertainty of 11.1 %. By reducing the limits of variation for operating voltage and electromagnetic compatibility as described above, a relative expanded standard uncertainty below 9.4 % could be achieved.

The target uncertainty of 7% (k = 2) can be achieved based on the above recommendations.

10 Summary of recommended updates of influence quantities and rated ranges

Influence quantities and performance characteristics	Minimum rated range	Limits of variation for reference-class dosimeters	Limits of variation for field-class dosimeters
Energy dependence of response	Section 5.1	Conventional: 4.5 % (full range) and 1.5 % (RQR, new RQC, RQA) Mammography: 1 %	5 % ^b
Dose linearity ^a	No change	1 %	2 % ^b
Resolution of reading		0.5 %	0.5 %

Stabilization time ^a		0.5 %	0.5 %
Long term stability		0.5 %	2 % ^b
Air kerma rate		1 %	2 % ^b
Angle of radiation incidence		1 %	1 %
Rotation (c.f., 7.1)	As stated by the manufacturer	0.5 %	0.5 %
Operation voltage	The performance of dosimeters should be investigated further for these influence quantities because the limit of variation is considered as not up to date with technical developments, c.f., 6.3.		
Air pressure			
Air pressure equilibrium time			
Temperature			
Electromagnetic compatibility			
Field size	A new definition is needed, c.f., 8.1.		

^aNot listed as a minimum rated range but mandatory requirement in a compliance test.

^bNot changed

11 Dissemination

These results were presented in the annual meeting of IEC SC62C WG 3 and to WG3 convenor in Berlin (Figure 1), May 2025. In addition, the document was shared with the IAEA CRP E24024 officers by email (Figure 2). The final document will also be shared with them by email after the final approval of MSU.

Figure 1. Stefan Pojtinger presenting the deliverable in the IEC SC62C WG 3 meeting in Berlin (photo taken by PaulaToroi)

The first deliverable of the TraMeXI project (D4)

Toroi Paula (STUK)

To

04/06/2025

Dear Zakithi and Olivera,

The first deliverable of our TraMeXI project is ready and I would like to share it with you. Based on our technical protocol we should "...write recommendations for the specific requirements such as compliance tests and rated ranges for reference- and field-class dosimeters to be updated in future revisions of IEC 61674:2012. These recommendations will be submitted to IEC SC62C WG 3, and IAEA SSDL officer and CRP E24024 group. Once the recommendations have been agreed by the consortium, the coordinator on behalf of PTB, ENEA, OPBG, SKBS, STUK, VINS and VSL will then submit it to EURAMET as D4: 'Recommendations on the specific requirements such as compliance tests and rated ranges for reference- and field-class dosimeters enabling traceable clinical measurements with the targeted uncertainty 7 % (k=2) and to be updated in future revisions of IEC 61674 and evidence submitted to IEC SC62C WG 3 and IAEA CRP E24024 officers'

This deliverable was already presented to the IEC group WG 3 in May.

This is just our recommendation at that point of time, but the situation is still changing a bit (see the email below) and we are just collecting further data which can then be used when the IEC standard is actually updated.

Best regards,
Paula

Figure 2. Email sent to the IAEA CRP E24024 officers dissemination of D4.